

Climate change and hunter-gatherers in montane eastern DR Congo

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Research Highlights

- Twa and Tembo perceived reduced rainfall and fog, but increased temperatures
- Meteorological data available shows reduced rainfall and increased temperatures
- Twa and Tembo reported reduced crop yields and reduced abundance of forest products
- Tembo are already implementing some climate adaptation, but not the Twa

Abstract

Mountain environments experience more rapid changes in temperature than lower elevations. However, little is known about the climatic changes already observed in African mountains, or the adaptation strategies used by hunter-gatherer communities. Semi-structured interviews were administered to 100 Twa hunter-gatherers living around Mt Kahuzi in eastern Democratic Republic of the Congo (DR Congo). We also organized 10 focus-group discussions with Tembo farmers living in the same area and we gathered historical from Kamembe meteorological station. Twa respondents perceived reduced rainfall and fog, and increased temperatures. They also reported reduced crop yields and abundance of forest products (caterpillars, mushrooms, honey). Tembo perceptions of climatic changes and impacts agreed with the Twa. Meteorological data available shows reduced rainfall and increased temperatures – but there are no records on fog. Despite being aware of climatic changes and impacts, Twa are not using any adaptation strategy, while Tembo farmers are using some (as they own land for farming or animal rearing, and are more business minded). For the Twa, their socioeconomic condition create high sensitivity to climate change and constrain adaptive capacity. To help the Twa, we recommend the use of “science with society” (SWS) participatory approach.

Keywords: Mountains; forests; local knowledge; adaptation; livelihood strategy

1. Introduction

There is increasing interest in local communities' perceptions of climatic changes, as a strategy for complementing meteorological data scarce areas, and as a way to better understand the impacts of climate change on the biophysical and the social systems at local scales (Klein et al., 2014; Reyes-García et al., 2016; Savo et al., 2016). Local communities'

53 knowledge can also be used to develop more effective and locally tailored strategies for
54 adapting to climatic change (Cuni-Sanchez et al., 2019a). A significant amount of the
55 literature about climate change perceptions and adaptation, and the socio-economic
56 parameters affecting both, has been published in the past decade (see Savo et al., 2016;
57 Reyes-García et al., 2016 for reviews). Most literature has focused on agricultural
58 communities, and therefore, documented impacts on the agricultural system and adaptation
59 strategies with regard to agriculture (Reyes-García et al., 2019). Relatively few studies have
60 documented pastoralist, fishing or hunter-gatherer communities' responses to climate change,
61 or documented the interaction between different communities in the same area. The reports
62 from IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) highlight an important information
63 gap regarding climate change impacts on hunting and wild food collection (Cramer et al.,
64 2014).

65
66 The Albertine Rift region of Africa (the western branch of the East African Rift, covering
67 parts of Uganda, the DR Congo, Rwanda, Burundi and Tanzania) is a climatically complex
68 transition zone between eastern and central equatorial Africa, spanning bimodal and
69 unimodal rainfall regime zones, and experiencing rain shadow effects from highly variable
70 topography (Salerno et al., 2019). Our understanding of this region's climatic patterns and
71 controls is still limited, largely due to the unreliable rain gauge coverage over central
72 equatorial Africa (Washington et al., 2013) and disagreement among satellite rainfall
73 products (Maidment et al., 2015; Salerno et al., 2019). While several studies using satellite-
74 based rainfall estimates reported a drying trend for the Congo Basin (e.g. Cook et al., 2020),
75 recent work from Uganda, which combined satellite and gauge-based rainfall estimates with
76 farmers' perceptions, reported wetting trends caused by increased rainfall during the rainy
77 seasons (Salerno et al., 2019). Changing seasons' lengths were also reported, which,
78 combined with wetter seasons, caused substantial declines in potato and bean harvests due to
79 fungal outbreaks and other diseases (Salerno et al., 2019).

80
81 The mountain forests of the Albertine Rift are particularly threatened by the predicted
82 displacement of people in response to climate-related changes in crop suitability (Phillipps &
83 Seimon, 2009; Watson & Segan, 2013). These mountain forests are also threatened by
84 climate change: a recent study showed that 76% of mountain forests' current extent will
85 experience different environmental conditions by 2070, challenging the continued existence
86 of these habitats, the biodiversity they harbour, and the ecosystem services they provide to
87 people (Ponce-Reyes et al., 2017). As the rate of warming is amplified with elevation,
88 mountain environments will differentially experience more rapid changes in temperature than
89 environments at lower elevations (Pepin et al., 2015). Raising temperatures affects cloud
90 formation (e.g. rising cloud base or reduced overall cloud incidence), further reducing water
91 inputs in mountain forests where leaves and branches from trees collect cloud/fog water
92 droplets (Bruijnzeel et al., 2011). Cloud/fog water harvesting by mountain forests can be of
93 key importance for local and regional livelihoods: e.g. in Mt Kenya, the deforestation which
94 occurred between 2000 and 2010 diminished dry-season river flows due to reduced fog water
95 harvesting, which reduced revenues from irrigated agriculture, hydropower and inland
96 fisheries, and increased costs of water treatment for potable use, costing Kenya over US\$33
97 million (UNEP, 2012).

98
99 Remarkably, little information is available on the changes observed in cloud or fog incidence
100 in the mountains of tropical Africa. In Mt Marsabit in Kenya, using a 30-year data of fog
101 occurrence recorded at a meteorological station, a 60% reduction in fog hours per year was
102 reported, which was in agreement with local communities' perceptions of changes in fog

103 occurrence (number of hours/days with fog) for the same time period (Cuni-Sanchez et al.,
104 2019a). Local communities in the East Usambaras in Tanzania also reported changes in fog
105 occurrence (Hamilton & Bensted-Smith, 1989). It is very likely that changes in fog
106 occurrence have been observed in the mountains of the Albertine Rift, but that it has not been
107 documented as studies have focused on lower altitudes (e.g. Bele et al., 2014) or, when
108 focused on mountain areas, did not investigate fog (e.g. Bomuhangi et al., 2016; Few et al.,
109 2017; Salerno et al., 2019; Zizinga et al., 2017).

110

111 Investigating local perceptions of climatic changes, and their impacts on the biophysical
112 system, can provide insights on appropriate adaptation strategies. For instance, a study
113 focused on farmers around Bukavu in DR Congo showed that non-timber forest products
114 (NTFPs) were considered as a safety net for when agricultural production failed (Bele et al.,
115 2014). In Cameroon, farmer communities also turn to forests when crops fail: e.g. they
116 replace groundnuts with seeds of the tree *Ricinodendron heudelotii* (Bele et al., 2013).
117 Farmer communities in both studies perceived NTFPs as being less affected by climatic
118 changes than agriculture (Bele et al., 2013; 2014). The Twa hunter-gatherers living in the
119 mountain forests near Bukavu, who use and value these forests differently to Bantu
120 agriculturalist communities (Cuni-Sanchez et al., 2019b), might report different changes in
121 NTFPs, and might also have different coping and adapting strategies to climatic changes
122 compared with farmers.

123

124 In tropical Africa there are about 1 million ‘Pygmy’ hunter-gatherers (Olivero et al., 2016).
125 The term Pygmy is often used to describe several ethnic groups (e.g., Aka, Baka, Bezan, Efe,
126 Twa, Mbuti, etc.) of short stature, who speak different languages, have different cultural and
127 morphological characteristics, and even live in diverse ecological areas, including lowland
128 and mountain forests (Verdu, 2016). Most of these ethnic groups are the poorest of the poor
129 in the areas where they live (e.g., Mbote: Batumike et al., 2020; Twa: Cuni-Sanchez et al.,
130 2019b), suggesting that they are particularly vulnerable to climatic changes, especially if
131 NTFPs abundance is being affected by climatic changes. However, to our knowledge, no
132 study has investigated if this is the case.

133

134 This paper, focused on the Twa hunter-gatherer communities of the mountain forests of Mt
135 Kahuzi in eastern DR Congo, aims at filling in these knowledge gaps regarding i) changes in
136 fog occurrence, ii) impacts of climate change on NTFPs, and iii) hunter-gatherer adaptation
137 strategies. The main objectives are to: (1) identify the changes in climate and their impacts on
138 the biophysical system as perceived by the Twa; (2) assess if these changes are consistent
139 with those perceived by nearby Tembo farmer communities and/or meteorological data
140 available in the region; and (3) determine which strategies Twa and farmers are using to
141 adapt to these climatic changes and their impacts. Given that socio-economic parameters such
142 as gender or wealth group might affect both perceptions of climate change and adaptation
143 strategies (see Savo et al., 2016), we also investigated the effects of gender and wealth group
144 on perceptions of climate change and adaptation strategies within the Twa. To our
145 knowledge, this is the first study focusing on local perceptions of climatic changes and their
146 impacts by forest hunter-gatherer communities in Africa. A study from Cameroon (Few et al.,
147 2017) included some hunter-gatherers but combined different livelihood-strategy groups
148 when analysing the data.

149

150 **2. Methodology**

151 **2.1. The study area**

152 This study focused on the communities living adjacent to Mt Kahuzi (3320m asl) in eastern
153 DR Congo (Fig. 1). Annual rainfall ranges between 1500 and 2000mm, mean annual
154 temperature is 20°C, and relative humidity is close to 76% (Fischer, 1996). The main habitat
155 types are submontane forests dominated by *Anonidium mannii*, *Carapa grandifolia*,
156 *Strombosia scheffleri* and *Trichilia welwichii*; and montane forests dominated by *Hagenia*
157 *abyssinica*, *Macaranga kilimandscharica* and *Rapanea melanophloeos* (Imani et al., 2016).
158 Bamboo (*Sinarundinaria alpina*) formations and alpine grasslands can be found at higher
159 altitudes. These forests are part of the Albertine Afromontane Biodiversity Hotspot
160 (Mittermeier et al., 2004), and support globally important populations of Grauer's gorilla
161 (*Gorilla beringei graueri*), eastern chimpanzee (*Pan troglodytes schweinfurthii*) and forest
162 elephant (*Loxodonta africana* var. *cyclotis*) (Plumptre et al., 2009).

163
164 Mt Kahuzi mountain forest is located within the Kahuzi-Biega National Park (NP) (Fig. 1).
165 Created as a Zoological and Forest Reserve in 1937, it became a National Park in 1970, when
166 human inhabitation in the park was prohibited and communities living inside (mainly the
167 Twa) were evicted with no compensation (Barume, 2000). The National Park was extended
168 into the lowlands in 1975, and more people were evicted (more Twa and other ethnic groups).
169 In 1981, it became a World Heritage Site, because of the remaining population of Grauer's
170 gorilla. In 1997, during the first Congo War, it was listed as a World Heritage Site in Danger
171 as a consequence of armed conflict in the eastern parts of the country. In 2020, it remains a
172 World Heritage Site in Danger because of illegal mining, bush meat hunting, presence of
173 mining villages within the park in the lowlands and presence of armed militia (who are
174 poaching and create a lack of security for park rangers to patrol). Access to Mt Kahuzi
175 mountain forest is restricted (hunting, farming or collection of NTFPs is illegal, Cuni-
176 Sanchez et al., 2019b).

177
178 The park is in one of the most densely populated areas of the country, surrounded by over
179 300 habitants/km², ICCN, 2009). The major ethnic groups around Mt Kahuzi are Twa
180 ('Pygmy' hunter-gatherers), Tembo and Shi (both Bantu farmers). We use livelihood strategy
181 (farmer or hunter-gatherer) to refer to the main activity used to provide food, shelter and
182 income for a given household, which, in our study area, is related to people's identity and
183 culture. Livelihood strategy not only involves making a living, it also means making it
184 meaningful (Bebbington, 2000). The Twa are the poorest members of the current society:
185 they are landless, they barely own domestic animals, they have limited access to education,
186 healthcare, microfinance or training opportunities, and they are continuously marginalized by
187 other ethnic groups (see Appendix A1 for details). Since Twa eviction from the national park
188 (their ancestral lands) most live in very small parcels of land borrowed from Tembo and Shi
189 farmers, where they have created 'villages' embedded within farmers' ones.

190 191 **2.2. Data collection among communities and analysis**

192 First, exploratory focus-group discussions (FGDs) were conducted with 4-7 male and female
193 elders in eight Twa villages located at similar altitudes on both sides (east/west) of Mt Kahuzi
194 (Fig. 1). These were used to design the semi-structured questionnaires and to build trust
195 among the Twa communities (see Appendix B). Then, we administered semi-structured
196 questionnaires to 100 Twa household heads (50 men and 50 women) in the same villages.
197 Questionnaires addressed household characteristics and assets, perceived changes in climate
198 and impacts on the biophysical environment, and adaptive strategies used to cope with or
199 adapt to observed changes (see Appendix B1 for details, including participant selection). The
200 exploratory FGDs and the interviews were translated and facilitated by the same Twa field
201 assistant. All participants (FGDs and interviews) were selected on a voluntary basis and were

202 first informed that the aim of the study was to better understand the perceived changes in
203 climate and its impacts. FGDs guiding questionnaire can be found in Appendix B2.

204

205 In order to compare Twa responses with those of farmers living in the area, FGDs were
206 organized in 10 Tembo villages (located on the western part of Mt Kahuzi, where 50% of the
207 Twa interviews had taken place, Fig. 1). Each FGD involved 4-8 elders (including the village
208 chief, as it is a custom in the area). We focused on elders as these have been living and
209 farming in a given area for a longer period of time (there is little migration in the
210 communities studied) and can potentially report a larger number of climatic changes and
211 impacts. These FGDs were facilitated and translated by one of the co-authors who is from the
212 Tembo ethnic group. All participants were selected on a voluntary basis. Participants were
213 first informed that the aim of the study was to better understand the perceived changes in
214 climate and its impacts. Then, informal discussions centred on perceived changes in climate
215 and impacts on the biophysical environment, and adaptive strategies used to cope with or
216 adapt to these changes (see Appendix B2).

217

218 We use ‘adaptive strategies’ to refer to (i) strategies which evolved to manage climate shocks
219 impacts ex-post (sometimes called ‘*coping strategies*’) and (ii) strategies which evolved to
220 reduce overall vulnerability to climate shocks (sometimes called ‘*true adaptive strategies*’).
221 We do not differentiate between both types as some strategies which start as ex-post
222 interventions in exceptional years can become ‘truly’ adaptation strategies for households or
223 whole communities over time (Morton, 2007). It could be argued that some ‘adaptive
224 strategies’ mentioned here are related to other non-climatic stresses such as population
225 growth or land use change, as we mention in the discussion.

226

227 For the Twa, the percent of respondents (n=100) was the main unit of analysis. To analyse
228 the effects of gender in the responses (males=50, females =50), the data were pooled per
229 gender. Then, data were pooled by wealth group (poor, average, wealthy) based on a wealth
230 index created from ten asset indicators (Córdova, 2008; Berman et al., 2014). Assets that
231 varied most across households were weighted greater than those more commonly found (see
232 Appendix A2). Paired T-test was used to assess significant differences between genders or
233 wealth groups. For the Tembo, data were pooled per FGDs (n=10) and thematic analysis
234 (Braun & Clarke, 2006) was used to identify the main themes of the discussions. Given the
235 different nature of the data, results from Twa (questionnaires) and Tembo (FGDs) should be
236 compared with caution, as e.g. FGDs might not be statistically representative samples of the
237 whole population in a region (Cruz-Garcia et al., 2019).

238

239 **2.3 Meteorological data**

240 Monthly rainfall, minimum (T_{\min}) and maximum (T_{\max}) monthly temperature (period 1971–
241 2019) were obtained from the Rwanda Meteorology Agency for Kamembe town
242 meteorological station (located at 1500 m asl, Fig. 1). There were missing values for rainfall
243 and temperature for the period 1994-1997 (extending to 1998 for temperature) and 2000-
244 2001, related to the political situation in Rwanda at that time. Although Lwiro meteorological
245 station is located closer to the Twa villages found in the eastern part of Mt Kahuzi, it has
246 missing values for longer periods. Akonkwa et al. (2015) compared rainfall and temperature
247 data from both stations (period 1971-2013) and found similar patterns. Annual values were
248 used to compute the 10-year running mean for rainfall. Seasonal averages refer to the dry
249 season (June-August) and the rainy season (September-May). Temporal trends for rainfall
250 and temperature were tested using a linear regression. Increased urbanization and urban heat

251 island effect is unlikely to be a driver of increased temperatures around Kamembe town
252 meteorological station given limited asphaltting and use of cement for construction.

253

254 **3. Results and discussion**

255 ***3.1 Perceptions of climatic changes and meteorological data***

256 Most Twa (>60% respondents) reported a reduction in the amount of rainfall and the length
257 of the rainy season (late onset) while a few respondents also mentioned an increase in dry
258 spells during the rainy season or increased showers during dry season (Fig. 2). Most Twa also
259 reported a reduction in fog (number of days with fog and quantity of fog), frost, strong winds
260 and hail storms (Fig. 2). About 50% of the Twa also reported warmer temperatures during the
261 dry season (Fig. 2). There were no significant differences between male and female
262 respondents (paired T-test, $p > 0.05$), see Fig. 2. This lack of differences between Twa male
263 and female perceptions differs from other studies: e.g. from farmers in Mt Elgon in Uganda,
264 or the Tsimane' and other peoples in the Amazon (Bomuhangi et al., 2016; Fernández-
265 Llamazares et al., 2017; Funatsu et al., 2019). Most likely the explanation is that contrary to
266 gender-based roles in other societies, both male and female Twa spend long periods of time
267 in the forest (female Twa also go hunting, and male Twa also collect NTFPs). Wealth did not
268 affect Twa responses (see Appendix A2). This is likely to be explained by the limited
269 differences between wealth groups in the Twa, with 'rich' Twa also being extremely poor,
270 e.g. owning a torch or a soap (not e.g. a car or solar panels). We could not explore the effects
271 of education or e.g. access to credit as none of the interviewees mentioned having access to
272 credit, and only two out of 100 had been to a primary school (see Appendix A2).

273

274

275 Overall, there were little differences on the climatic changes reported by Twa and Tembo
276 (although we used different methods, household questionnaires vs FGDs, respectively).
277 Tembo reported the same direction of change as Twa for amount of rainfall, dry spells,
278 showers, temperatures, fog and hail storms, but opposite direction of change for length of the
279 rainy season and wind (Table 2). It is possible that most Tembo mentioned increased length
280 of the rainy season because of a perceived increase in showers during the dry season (Table
281 2). The percent of respondents who mentioned an increase in dry spells during the rainy
282 season was also greater for Tembo than for the Twa (>70% compared with <25% for the
283 Twa, Table 2). It is likely that more Tembo reported these changes (compared with Twa)
284 because for most Tembo farming is their main livelihood activity, and they have to pay
285 particular attention to these changes due to the effects they have on crop yields and pests (dry
286 spells cause crop failure and showers increase pest prevalence). The overall agreement
287 between Twa and Tembo perceptions of climatic changes support the notion that groups
288 having different livelihood strategies but living in the same area report similar changes in
289 climate (e.g. Cuni-Sanchez et al., 2012; 2019a).

290

291 Climatic changes reported by Twa (and Tembo) agree with farmers' perceptions in the
292 Bukavu area, who also reported increased temperatures, shorter and less rainfall during the
293 rainy season, dry spells during rainy season, rain showers during dry season, and increased
294 strong winds during rainy season (Bele et al., 2014). Compared with other studies in
295 mountains in the Albertine Rift region, increased temperatures were also reported by farmers
296 in the Rwenzori Mts, while a late (or unpredictable) onset of the rainy season was also
297 reported in Kibale NP and Volcanos NP (Few et al., 2017; Hartter et al., 2012; Zizinga et al.,
298 2017). Overall reduced rainfall was reported from Kibale NP, like in our study, but increased
299 rainfall, mostly due to fewer but heavier precipitation events, was reported in the Rwenzori
300 Mts (Harterter et al., 2012; Zizinga et al., 2017). Although there is limited certainty about

301 future rainfall projections in tropical Africa, projected changes in rainfall by late century
302 (2071–2100, RCP4.5) indicate divergent patterns in different mountains in the region: e.g.
303 decreased amount of rainfall in eastern DR Congo, Volcanos NP and the Rwenzori Mts, but
304 increased amount in Kibale NP (Platts et al., 2015). Divergent patterns in rainfall seasonality
305 have also been predicted for the different mountains (Platts et al., 2015).

306

307 The study in Bukavu did not report changes in fog or hail storms (Bele et al., 2014), which
308 are likely to be restricted to higher altitudes than those they studied. In terms of the reported
309 changes in fog (shared by both ethnic groups), this study adds to the few case-studies
310 available for African mountains, which also reported a reduction in both quantity and number
311 of fog days (Cuni-Sanchez et al., 2019a; Hamilton & Bensted-Smith, 1989). With regard to
312 hailstorms, eastern DR Congo is recognized for frequent hailstorms, compared with the rest
313 of Africa (Frisby & Sansom, 1967). It is known that with increased temperatures, increased
314 amounts of moisture in the air can lead to heavier precipitation during an individual storm,
315 including hail. Contrary to our findings, communities in Mt Elgon in Uganda (which is not in
316 the Albertine Rift region) reported increased hailstorm frequency (Bomuhangi et al., 2016). A
317 recent study showed an increase in extent and intensity of thunderstorms observed over the
318 Congo Basin (Raghavendra et al., 2018), but, to our knowledge, no studies have focused on
319 quantifying changes in hail storms in the region.

320

321 No trend in annual rainfall was observed at Kamembe meteorological station, but a
322 significant decrease for the 10-year running mean was found (Fig. 3). A similar significant
323 trend was observed for the 10-year running mean of the rainy season (September-May), but
324 no trend was found for the dry season (June-August) (see Appendix A3). A significant trend
325 in T_{\max} was observed (Fig. 4), but not for T_{\min} or for temperature range (Figure not included).
326 A significant trend in T_{\max} for the dry season (June-August) was also observed (see Appendix
327 A3).

328

329 Overall, the historical meteorological data available from Kamembe is consistent with the
330 narratives from local peoples with regard to changes in a) rainfall during the rainy season
331 (reduced amount) and b) temperature during the dry season (greater T_{\max}). Unfortunately, we
332 were unable to obtain daily values to investigate the narratives from local people in further
333 detail (e.g. late onset rainy season); and there is no fog data available for this station. Several
334 authors have shown the agreement between local perceptions on climatic changes and
335 meteorological data (see Savo et al., 2016 for a review). Mountain regions characterized by
336 high topographic heterogeneity, modelling and remote sensing data may fail to capture spatial
337 climatic heterogeneity on the ground (Platts et al., 2013; 2015). In such mountain regions
338 where meteorological data is scarce, local perceptions of climate variability can help increase
339 our knowledge on the climatic changes observed (e.g. Savo et al., 2016; Cuni-Sanchez et al.,
340 2019a).

341

342 **3.2 Perceived impacts of the climatic changes**

343 Most Twa (>70% respondents) reported a decrease in floods, stream flow, landslides and soil
344 erosion (Fig. 2). In terms of changes in the biological domain, most Twa (>70% respondents)
345 mentioned a reduction in the abundance of caterpillars, honey, mushroom and crabs, a
346 reduction in fruit yields of wild fruiting plants and that some tree and wild animal species had
347 become rare (Fig. 5). They also reported a decrease in yields of several crops (Fig. 5). There
348 were no differences between male and female respondents (Fig. 5) except for two
349 observations: only a few men reported a decrease in Marihuana yields and only a few females
350 reported a decrease in wild yam abundance (activities restricted to males and females,

351 respectively). As abovementioned, the lack of differences between Twa male and female
352 perceptions differs from other studies (Bomuhangi et al., 2016; Fernández-Llamazares et al.,
353 2017; Funatsu et al., 2019) and is likely to be related to limited gender-based roles in Twa
354 society. Wealth did not affect Twa responses regarding the impacts of climatic changes (see
355 Appendix A2).

356
357 Remarkably, contrary to the Twa, most Tembo mentioned an increase decrease in floods,
358 stream flow, landslides and soil erosion, which is completely opposite to what most Twa
359 reported (Fig. 2, Table 1). These divergent perceptions can be explained by the fact that
360 Tembo own land for farming (which may be damaged by floods, landslides and soil erosion),
361 and that they live in larger villages. About 50% of the Twa respondents live in the same area
362 where Tembo live (western part of Mt Kahuzi), so local topography such as slope or aspect is
363 unlikely to explain these differences in direction of change. While Twa respondents did not
364 have an explanation for the reported changes in the physical environment, most Tembo
365 mentioned that these changes were related to deforestation in the area, with comments such
366 as e.g. *'Now there is less forest on top of hills, that is why there is more soil erosion and*
367 *landslides'*. It is possible that Tembo perceptions reflect increased storm intensity -something
368 we could not confirm with meteorological data available.

369
370 Increased floods was reported by farmers in Bukavu area (Bele et al., 2014), while increased
371 soil erosion associated with heavy rains was also reported by local famers living around
372 Volcanos NP, and increased floods and landslides were reported in Mt Elgon NP (Bomuhangi
373 et al., 2016; Few et al., 2017). In Mt Elgon NP in Uganda, an increase in landslides over time
374 has been attributed to changing landuse patterns, including increased numbers of settlements
375 and farms on steep slopes, as well as prolonged rainfall of low intensities, which has high
376 chances of infiltrating and soaking the soil thus increasing the chances of landslides over
377 steep slopes (Kitutu et al., 2011; Masaba et al., 2017). It is possible that increased
378 urbanization among the Tembo (which in some cases pushes people to construct houses on
379 steep slopes), might have also affected perceptions with regard to landslides.

380
381 In terms of changes in the biological domain, Tembo responses (from FGDs) agreed with
382 Twa responses (from questionnaires) (Table 2). The only difference was the tree species
383 discussed: Tembo mentioning cultivated tree species instead of wild ones (Table 2).
384 Compared with other studies in the region, reduced crop yields and increased disease
385 prevalence were also reported as consequences of changing rainfall patterns in Volcanos NP
386 in Rwanda (Few et al., 2017) and in Kibale NP and the Rwenzori Mts in Uganda (Salerno et
387 al., 2019). The observed decline in abundance of several NTFPs (caterpillar, honey,
388 mushroom and crabs), and the reported relationship with climatic changes, is in disagreement
389 with Bele et al. (2014), who, focusing on farmers in the nearby Bukavu area, reported these
390 products as being less affected by climatic changes than agriculture. Farmers who mainly
391 only harvest NTFPs when crops fail are likely to have lower awareness NTFPs change over
392 time –given their intermittent interaction with these. In Cameroon, local residents (some of
393 which were hunter-gatherers) also reported a decrease in NTFPs availability, related to
394 deforestation and increased demand (Few et al., 2017). Several studies have highlighted that
395 forests can be used as source of food when crops fail (e.g. Cuni-Sanchez et al., 2012; Balama
396 et al., 2017). However, few have investigated changes in NTFPs abundance over time, related
397 to climatic changes or other factors. For instance, two recent publications have highlighted
398 changes in edible caterpillar abundance in Cameroon, related to logging and perceptions of
399 climatic changes (Muvatsi et al., 2018; Ngute et al., 2019). More research on the impacts of
400 climatic changes on NTFPs is needed.

401

402 For the Twa the perceived causes of the observed reduction in NTFPs' abundance were
403 climatic, but that for wildlife it was overhunting (Table 3). Ancestors' will – with comments
404 such as '*the ancestors have left with their treasures, as we are no longer taking care of the*
405 *forest*' - were mentioned by a few participants. Note that Twa have a view of nature where
406 humans (Twa) have to take care of Nature (the forest) (see Cuni-Sanchez et al., 2019b). The
407 perceived cause of all the observed changes in the biological domain for the Tembo was
408 deforestation. Tembo respondents explained that: e.g. '*before there were more patches of*
409 *forest between farmers' fields, the area was more humid and cooler and avocado trees*
410 *produced more fruits*' and '*before there were more forest patches with insects, which would*
411 *eat the pests of cassava, now there are fewer forests and insects, and cassava is more sick*'.
412 Perceived changes in crop yields could also be related to nutrient depletion in the soils,
413 related to shorter fallow rotations. Preliminary investigations show that fallow rotations have
414 been significantly reduced in Tembo farms (ongoing research).

415

416

417 **3.3. Twa and Tembo adaptive strategies or lack of**

418 Twa did not report using any adaptive strategy to the observed changes in climate and their
419 impacts, although they did recognize that climatic changes and impacts in the biophysical
420 domain (as shown above). They said that the greatest change for them was the fact that they
421 had been evicted from the forest, forcing them to change their livelihood strategy (hunter-
422 gathering), but they had been given no land to e.g. start farming or rearing animals. A study
423 focused on Twa living near Bwindi Impenetrable Forest NP in Uganda showed that child
424 mortality (under five years of age) was 59% for households without land while only 18% for
425 households with land (Balenger et al., 2005), which highlights the importance of access to
426 farming land for household nutrition, health and well-being. Most of our Twa study
427 participants cultivate < 0.01 ha of land- if they have any (see Appendix A). As highlighted in
428 Indonesian Papua, for some indigenous peoples, there are more pressing issues than climate
429 change impacts (Boissiere et al., 2013). Climate change will likely exacerbate Twa current
430 food insecurity because the landless Twa have fewer opportunities (e.g. no land to grow
431 improved seed varieties). This is another example of how policies made by those living
432 outside of the mountains can reduce climate adaptation options (Yeh et al, 2014; Klein et al,
433 2019).

434

435 Contrary to the Twa, the Tembo have used a range of strategies to adapt to the observed
436 changes in climate and their impacts, mostly related to growing new crops or crop varieties,
437 cultivating larger farms (to compensate for lower yields), rearing animals, or complementing
438 farming with other off-farm activities, such as mining, timber harvesting or charcoal
439 production (Table 4). These strategies -including the diversification of livelihoods- are often
440 mentioned by farmers elsewhere in Africa (e.g. Cuni-Sanchez et al., 2012; Zizinga et al.,
441 2017). Changing planting dates, soil conservation practices, irrigation and agroforestry,
442 mentioned by farmers e.g. in the Rwenzori Mts (Zizinga et al., 2017), and were not
443 mentioned by the Tembo. Most likely these are limited in our study area due to the
444 unpredictability of the onset of the rainy season, steep slopes near streams which make
445 irrigation difficult, lack of training and funds to start soil conservation and agroforestry
446 practices (participants' comments during FGDs).

447

448 While most of the strategies mentioned by the Tembo have been initiated by NGOs, two
449 strategies were initiated by the farmers themselves: i) the cultivation of a fast-growing variety
450 of maize, and ii) the cultivation of pineapples. In both cases, the initiatives were driven by a

451 combination of climatic and economic drivers: maize is high in demand in Bitale village due
452 to the presence of miners from other ethnic groups who prefer this to cassava as a staple
453 (contrary to Twa and Tembo people); moreover, farmers believe that pineapples are better
454 adapted to drought than other crops and they can sell them to MONUSCO staff (MONUSCO
455 is the French acronym of The United Nations Organization Stabilization Mission in DR
456 Congo). Remarkably, using forest products as a safety-net was not mentioned in any Tembo
457 FGDs, which is different from a previous study on farmers in Bukavu area (Bele et al., 2014),
458 and in Volcanos NP in Rwanda (Few et al., 2017).

459

460 Our study approach has some limitations. First, we compared questionnaire data from Twa
461 with FGDs data from Tembo elders only (see Table 1 and 2). Although FGDs can help have a
462 general understanding of a topic in a given area, a larger number of questionnaires can
463 provide more detailed insights, particularly if they cover a wider range of household heads'
464 age classes. We recommend further work using questionnaires for the Tembo, which could
465 help investigate the effects of gender and wealth within this ethnic group. Second, we only
466 used data from one meteorological station. Combining data from different stations is
467 preferred, especially if some are located within the villages surveyed. Increased use of
468 automatic weather stations or gauges could help reduce this challenge.

469

470 ***4. Implications of the results and conclusions***

471 Our findings have four major implications. First, climatic changes have already been
472 perceived by local communities in the mountains of eastern DR Congo, which are supported
473 by meteorological data available from a nearby station (for rainfall and temperature), and
474 which agree with changes reported by farmers in other mountains of the Albertine Rift.
475 Notably, local communities highlighted reduced fog, which plays an important role in the
476 ecology of mountain forests in the region. Despite its importance, fog is not recorded by most
477 meteorological stations (but see Cuni-Sanchez et al., 2019a; Los et al., 2019 for Kenya).
478 Local perceptions of climate variability can help increase our knowledge on the climatic
479 changes observed, and their impacts (e.g. Savo et al., 2016; Cuni-Sanchez et al., 2019a).
480 Several authors have called for greater integration of indigenous knowledge and experience
481 in IPCC assessment reports (e.g. Ford et al., 2016). We provide evidence of how indigenous
482 peoples can provide insights for variables beyond rainfall and temperature (e.g. fog,
483 hailstorms).

484

485 Second, we report that Twa are not using any adaptation strategy, which is not related to a
486 lack of perception of changes in climate or in the biological domain. The key reason is that
487 their livelihood base (hunter-gathering inside the park) has become illegal; and issues of
488 power, land tenure, and access are much more tangible. These issues will likely exacerbate
489 Twa's vulnerability to climatic changes, including food insecurity, in the nearby future. Twa
490 hunter-gatherers are found around several parks in the Albertine Rift, including e.g. Volcanos
491 NP in Rwanda, studied by Few et al. (2017) (see Fig. 1). But these authors did not investigate
492 the differences in perceptions and adaptation -or lack of- between farmers and the Twa. A
493 study focused on vulnerability of health to climate change in Twa villages around Bwindi
494 Impenetrable Forest NP in Uganda also highlighted that their vulnerability is largely driven
495 by socioeconomic conditions which create high sensitivity to climate change and constrain
496 adaptive capacity (Berrang-Ford et al., 2012). Preliminary data from Kibira NP in Burundi
497 also indicates that the Twa are facing a similar situation: no adaptation to climatic changes
498 because limited livelihood options following eviction. To help Twa adapt to climatic changes,
499 we recommend the use of "science with society" (SWS) participative (or transdisciplinary)
500 approach (Steger et al., 2021), an iterative process that brings together actors (including local

501 communities) to engage in knowledge co-production: in this case, to identify the best
502 pathway towards adaptation. Notably, given that Twa are a marginalized remote community,
503 the longer-term actions towards increasing desirable forms of resilience need to take account
504 short-term realities and needs, including food security (Maru et al., 2014).

505
506 Third, contrary to the Twa, Tembo farmers already use some adaptive strategies. Although
507 the effectiveness of the strategies reported here should be assessed, this study provides new
508 ideas which could be tested in other mountain areas in the region (e.g. pineapple cultivation).
509 The off-farm activities mentioned most often (mining, timber harvesting, charcoal
510 production) can have severe impacts on the natural environment (e.g. pollution related to
511 small-scale gold mining) that can further compound the wider impacts of climate change.
512 More support (such as training and access to micro-finance to start animal rearing) could help
513 reduce the use of these unsustainable off-farm activities (comments' made by Tembo during
514 FGDs). Our data on adaptation strategies used by Tembo contributes to filling in the data gap
515 on indigenous adaptation strategies used in Central Africa (Petzold et al., 2020), key
516 information needed if the IPCC is to better integrate indigenous knowledge (e.g. Ford et al.,
517 2016, Petzold et al., 2020).

518
519 Fourth, relying more heavily on forests was not mentioned as an adaptive strategy by any
520 group studied (farmers or hunter-gatherers), due to the perceived reduction in forest products.
521 This is different from other studies in Africa, where such products are used as a safety net
522 when crops fail. This finding is particularly important: the lack of this safety net makes these
523 communities even more vulnerable to climatic changes, particularly the Twa, which still
524 heavily rely on forests for their livelihoods (see Appendix A1).

525
526 If we are to help the most vulnerable communities in society -e.g. hunter-gatherers- adapt to a
527 changing climate, we need to acknowledge that they have different vulnerability and
528 adaptation potential than nearby farmer communities. For example, if they do not have access
529 to land, they cannot use improved seed varieties as an adaptation option. Instead of focusing
530 on their weaknesses (limited farming skills), interventions should focus on diversifying
531 livelihoods using their existing strengths (e.g. caterpillar rearing, see Cuni-Sanchez et al.,
532 2019b; pottery, Ndayizeye et al., 2020). Overall, this research contributes to the still limited
533 but emerging knowledge base to inform the identification of adaptation needs and
534 opportunities in highly vulnerable indigenous populations in Africa.

535
536

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541

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Tables and figures

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Fig. 1 Study area and selected Twa villages (1500-1900m asl) and Tembo villages (1400-1900m asl). Kamembe Meteorological station is at 1500 m asl. NP refers to National Park. Twa hunter-gatherers are also found around Kibira NP, Volcanos NP and Bwindi NP.

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800 **Fig. 2** Perceived changes in climate and physical environment, as reported by male (n=50) and female (n=50)
 801 Twa respondents. Responses between male and female respondents are not significantly different (paired T-test
 802 p=0.08).
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806 **Fig. 3** Annual rainfall for Kamembe Meteorological station, 1500 m asl. Grey line refers to annual rainfall and
 807 black line refers to the 10-year running average. Trend for annual rainfall is not significant (line not included)
 808 but trend for running mean (thin black line) is significant at $p < .05$ ($R^2 = 0.44$). Missing values (1994-1997 and
 809 2000-2001) relate to the political situation in Rwanda at that time. Note that 2016-2017 were the driest years on
 810 record, related to the greatest 'El Nino' event in central Africa (Bennett et al. 2021).
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819 **Fig. 4** Annual maximum temperature for Kamembe Meteorological station, 1500 m. Grey line refers to annual
820 maximum temperature. Trend is significant at $p < .05$ ($R^2 = 0.62$). Missing values (1994-1998 and 2000-2001)
821 relate to the political situation in Rwanda at that time.

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825 **Fig. 5** Perceived changes in non-timber forest products, wild animals and trees, domestic animals and crops, as
 826 reported by male (n=50) and female (n=50) Twa respondents. For wild fruits the trees *Myrianthus holstii*,
 827 *Dacryodes klaineana* and the lianas *Landolphia owariensis* were those most commonly mentioned. The wild
 828 yam species most frequently harvested is likely to be *Dioscorea praehensilis*. Guinea pig rearing was first
 829 introduced to Twa by an NGO in 1995. Responses between male and female respondents are not significantly
 830 different (paired T-test p=0.14).
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836 **Table 1** Comparison between perceived changes in climatic variables and in the physical domain as reported by
 837 Twa hunter-gatherers (n=100 questionnaires) and Tembo farmers (n=10 focus-group discussions). * denotes
 838 opposite direction of change.

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	Twa hunter-gatherers	Tembo farmers	
Rainfall during rainy season	↓ (78%)	↓ (90%)	
Length of rainy season	↓ (61%)	↑ (60%)	*
Dry spells during rainy season	↑ (21%)	↑ (70%)	
Showers during dry season	↑ (12%)	↑ (80%)	
Temperatures during dry season	↑ (47%)	↑ (90%)	
Days with fog during rainy season	↓ (89%)	↓ (70%)	
Quantity of fog during rainy season	↓ (83%)	↓ (80%)	
Frost	↓ (81%)	No change	*
Strong winds during rainy season	↓ (81%)	↑ (70%)	*
Hail storms	↓ (94%)	↓ (90%)	
Floods during rainy season	↓ (87%)	↑ (70%)	*
Stream flow during rainy season	↓ (86%)	↑ (90%)	*
Landslides	↓ (90%)	↑ (60%)	*
Soil erosion during rainy season	↓ (86%)	↑ (80%)	*

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845 **Table 2** Comparison between perceived changes in the biological domain as reported by Twa hunter-gatherers
 846 (n=100 questionnaires) and Tembo farmers (n=10 focus-group discussions). * for the Twa fruiting trees are trees
 847 found in the wild (e.g. *Myrianthus holstii*, *Dacryodes klaineana*) but for the Tembo fruiting trees are cultivated
 848 species (e.g. mango, avocado, banana).

	Twa hunter-gatherers (%)	Tembo farmers (%)
Lower caterpillar abundance in the forest	92%	60%
Less wild honey in the forest	88%	50%
Lower mushroom abundance in the forest	92%	80%
Lower crab abundance in the streams	78%	
Some tree species have become rare	59%	100%
Some animal species have become rare	92%	100%
Some tree species produce fewer fruits*	73%	90%
Cassava yields have reduced	66%	60%
Beans yields have reduced	57%	40%
Maize yields have reduced	12%	10%
Groundnut yields have reduced		70%
Goats produce fewer offspring		90%
Chicken have more diseases		80%

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851 **Table 3** Perceived causes of the observed changes in the biological domain as reported by Twa respondents
 852 (n=100).

	Caterpillars	Wild honey	Mushrooms	Crabs	Wild fruits	Wild animals	Crop yields
Reduced rainfall	21%	10%	22%	6%	11%		3%
Increased temperatures	3%	2%	8%	2%	11%	1%	1%
Increased wind	1%				1%		
More hail storms					1%		
Decreased stream flow				12%			
Deforestation/habitat destruction	18%	2%	2%			7%	
Overhunting/overharvesting				8%		72%	
Decreased soil fertility							13%
Increased pests and diseases							60%
God's will	2%	2%			2%	2%	
Ancestors' will	10%	10%	10%		2%	12%	

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857 **Table 4** Adaptive strategies mentioned by the Tembo farmers (n=10 focus-group discussions or FGDs). * refers
858 to activities promoted by an NGO. Off-farm activities include e.g. being involved in small-scale mining, small-
859 scale timber harvesting or charcoal production.
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Adaptation strategy	Tembo farmers
To grow new varieties of cassava resistant to diseases*	100%
To grow new varieties of maize	10%
To grow new varieties of beans (fast-maturing)*	50%
To grow new crops (soya)* (pineapple)	50%
To start farming near streams (to irrigate)	20%
To cultivate larger farms to compensate for low yields	60%
To start rearing animals (goat, chicken)*	100%
To complement farming with other off-farm activities	80%

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